

Agro2Circular

D1.8 – Energy Management Plan (Draft)

November 2023

Authors: Clara Navarro Van Iseghem (REG); Victor Fabregat Tena (REG)

Technical references

Project Acronym	Agro2Circular
Project Title	TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR
Project Coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó Sánchez CETEC fuensanta.monzo@agro2circular.org
Project Duration	October 2021 – September 2024 (36 months)
Deliverable No.	D1.8
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 1 – A2C Specifications, Residues Management and Data Integration System
Task	T1.3 – A2C water and energy efficiency assurance
Lead beneficiary	11 (REGENERA)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	1 (CETEC), 3 (SAPERATEC), 4 (IRIS), 6 (EPOCH), 7 (CETBIO), 8 (UNIMIB), 13 (CTNC)
Due date of deliverable	30 September 2022
Actual submission date	30 September 2022

* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	Date	Comments
v0.1	08/09/2022	First draft of document
v0.2	19/09/2022	Revised version based on the comments of Sofía Martínez - CTNC and Fuensanta Monzó - CETEC
v1.0	30/09/2022	First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
v2.0	24/11/2023	Second version after review according to the comments from REPA1

Document Distribution Log

Version	Date	Distributed to
v0.1	08/09/2022	Fuensanta Monzó Sánchez and Sofía Martínez
v1.0	30/09/2022	Fuensanta Monzó Sánchez and Jaime Ortiz Aragón
V2.0	24/11/2023	Fuensanta Monzó

Verification and approval

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Jaime Ortiz Aragón (ECOTRACE)	24/11/2023
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó Sánchez (CETEC)	24/11/2023

Disclaimer and acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036838

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the views of the author(s) the European Research Executive Agency (REA) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. Whilst efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and completeness of this document, the A2C consortium shall not be liable for any errors or omissions, however caused.

Table of contents

1	Executive summary	7
2	Introduction	8
3	Energy Management Plan	9
4	Processes description.....	10
4.1	Process 1: Green hybrid technologies for extraction of bioactive substances from agrifood wastes	13
4.1.1	Description	13
4.1.2	Energy performance assessment	15
4.2	Process 2: New food, nutraceuticals & cosmetic formulations using extracts from agrifood wastes.	15
4.2.1	Description	15
4.2.2	Energy performance assessment	16
4.3	Process 3: Identification and sorting of multilayer materials	17
4.3.1	Description	17
4.3.2	Energy performance assessment	18
4.4	Process 4: Separation of aluminium (Al) from complex multilayer structures 18	
4.4.1	Description	18
4.4.2	Energy performance assessment	19
4.5	Process 5: PET/PE enzymatic depolymerisation	20
4.5.1	Description	20
4.5.2	Energy performance assessment	21
4.6	Process 6: Plastics decontamination	21
4.6.1	Description	21
4.6.2	Energy performance assessment	22
4.7	Process 7: Aluminium recycling and chemical modification	22
4.7.1	Description	22
4.7.2	Energy performance assessment	22
4.8	Process 8: Upcycling of enzymatic degradation products (alkanes, TPA, EG) by cell factories	22
4.8.1	Description	22
4.8.2	Energy performance assessment	23
4.9	Process 9: PHBV and C-50 carotenoids development by <i>Hfx. mediterranei</i> haloarchaea cell factory	23
4.9.1	Description	23
4.9.2	Energy performance assessment	24
4.10	Process 10: High barrier compounds by extensional flow mixing and compatibilisation	24
4.10.1	Description	24
4.10.2	Energy performance assessment.....	24
5	Conclusions and next steps.....	25

List of Tables

Table 1. Information relating to the processes studied.	12
Table 2. The fruits and vegetables wastes used for revalorization.	14
Table 3. Extraction and purification technologies.....	14
Table 4. Material balance of the process.	19
Table 5. Process energy demand.	19
Table 6. Process 4 energy consumption.....	19
Table 7. Energy consumption of the process.....	24

List of Figures

Figure 1. Energy management guide.....	9
Figure 2. Flowchart of the extraction and revalorisation of food waste from the agrifood industry.....	13
Figure 3. Multilayer aseptic bags upcycling.	16
Figure 4. Multilayer soil disinfection films.....	17

List of abbreviations

A2C	Agro2Circular
AE	Assisted extraction
GS	Green solvents
EAE	Enzymatic assisted extraction
UAE	Ultrasound assisted extraction
MAE	Microwave assisted extraction
SFE	Supercritical fluid extraction
PE	Polyethylene
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PA	Polyamide
EVOH	Ethylene vinyl alcohol
HDPE	High-density polyethylene
LDPE	Low-density polyethylene
LLDPE	Linear Low-density polyethylene
PHBV	Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoate
TPA	Terephthalic acid
EG	Ethylene glycol
PCA	Protocatechuic acid
GA	Glycolic acid
OTR	Oxygen Permeability Test
EMP	Energy Management Plan
VOCs	Volatile Organic Compounds

1 Executive summary

This deliverable presents a draft of the energy management plan for the processes and technologies developed in the Agro2Circular, with the aim that once they increase their TRL and reach a semi-industrial scale, they become as efficient and sustainable as possible.

Due to the fact that the processes are at a very early stage, in this first draft it has only been possible to present some consumption analyses of those processes that are a little more advanced. Some of them have not yet started at this stage of the project.

Over the following months, more information will be gathered from the partners who are carrying out the development of the different processes addressed in the projects, so that more precise data can be obtained on their consumption and possible scaling.

Once analysed, a series of more specific recommendations can be made for each one, as well as the calculation of KPIs and consumption in a more precise and reliable way.

With all this data, it will be possible to assess their profitability on a semi-industrial scale.

2 Introduction

The objective of this deliverable is the analysis of the energy requirements of the A2C technologies and processes including time of use, life cycle and load, aimed to optimise the key parameters to reach the maximum energy savings.

Due to the fact that one of the objectives of the project is the scalability of the processes, which will go from a TRL between 4 and 5 to one between 6 and 7, increasing all their TRL in 2 steps, this study of the energy requirements will analyse their viability on a large scale. Therefore, it will be possible to estimate more accurately their energy cost in pre industrial plants, as well as their energy optimisation and the use of renewable energies.

In order to carry out the scalability of the processes, and consequently their TRL increase, the processes will be implemented and studied in pilot plants, obtaining real data of their operation.

Therefore, in this deliverable, which is a draft of the Energy Management Plan, an approximate study has been made of the expected energy requirements of the processes in the pilot plants, which will be compared with the real results obtained.

In addition, the other aim of the Energy Management Plan is to establish an energy efficiency guideline for each of the processes being developed at A2C in order to make them as efficient and sustainable as possible.

3 Energy Management Plan

An Energy Management Plan (EMP) is a broad-reaching document that serves as a long-term planning resource and is used by an entity to drive and guide progress toward a more secure, cost-effective and sustainable energy future. An EMP must include, at a minimum, an energy reduction goal and an implementation plan to achieve that goal.

The Guidelines for Energy Management follow seven main steps that are illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 1. Energy management guide.

As mentioned above, the objective of this deliverable is the definition of an EMP for the processes being investigated. In this case, an EMP for a process under development involves the detailed study of its operation, the forecast of its consumption, the establishment of KPIs and the regulation of the necessary systems to improve energy performance, aiming at the energy efficiency of the process and the possible use of renewable energies.

Due to the fact that the processes are not yet 100% defined, this draft studies the expected consumptions of the processes in their final stage. Therefore, firstly, the energy consumption of each process in its initial phase will be studied in detail. In this phase, the times of use of each phase of the process, the estimated useful life of each piece of equipment and its power will be detailed.

4 Processes description

All the processes in this project aim to upgrade and recycle waste from the agri-food chain: such as organic compounds from fruit and vegetables, post-industrial food contaminated plastics from packaging and the agricultural barrier films.

The processes can be divided into two main branches: (1) those focused on the revalorisation of fruit and vegetable waste and (2) those focused on the recycling of plastics used in industry for food packaging and as agriculture barrier films.

Within group (1) are processes 1 and 2 and in group (2) are the rest. These processes can be visualised schematically in the following table.

PROCESS	DESCRIPTION	TASKS INVOLVED	SUBTASK	START MONTH	END MONTH	START TRL	END TRL	PILOT SCALE UP
1	Green hybrid technologies for extraction of bioactive substances from agrifood wastes	2.1	-	2	16	5	7	Rute 1: Extraction 100 kg/h and purification 15 kg Rute 2: Extraction 50 kg/h and purification 15 kg
		2.2	2.2.1					
			2.2.2					
		2.3	2.3.1	8	16			
2	New food, nutraceuticals & cosmetic formulations using extracts from agrifood wastes	2.3	2.3.2	8	16	5	7	Delivery systems up to 1 kg
		2.4	-					
3	Identification and sorting of multilayer materials	3.2	3.2.1	2	22	4	6	Multilayers sorting flow rates of 25 kg/h
			3.2.2					
			3.2.3					
4	Separation of aluminium (Al) from complex multilayer structures	3.3	3.3.1	3	22	5	7	Pilot plant up to 20 kg batches
			3.3.2					
			3.3.3					
5	PET/PE enzymatic depolymerisation	3.4	3.4.1	3	22	4	6	Pilot plant: 50-80 kg of PET/PE pre-treated, 30 L reactor for enzymes production and a 50 L bioreactor and a
			3.4.2					
			3.4.3					

PROCESS	DESCRIPTION	TASKS INVOLVED	SUBTASK	START MONTH	END MONTH	START TRL	END TRL	PILOT SCALE UP
6	Plastics decontamination	3.1	3.1.1	2	9	5	7	1.000 L/day of wastewater filtered and 500 kg of plastics decontamination
		3.5	3.1.2					
7	Aluminium recycling and chemical modification	3.5	3.5.1	7	22	4	6	Pilot scale up to 1 kg
			3.5.2					
8	Upcycling of enzymatic degradation products (alkanes, TPA, EG) by cell factories	5.1	5.1.1	13	22	4	6	Pilot scale up to 30 L
9	PHBV and C-50 carotenoids development by Hfx mediterranei haloarchaea cell factory	5.1	5.1.2	13	22	4	6	Pilot scale up to 100 L and extraction process to 1-3L
10	High barrier compounds by extensional flow mixing and compatibilisation	5.2	5.2.1	13	22	5	7	Pilot scale up to 1.000 kg of capacity
			5.2.2					

Table 1. Information relating to the processes studied.

Each of the technologies to be studied is explained in more detail below:

(1) Green hybrid extraction, purification & stabilisation routes for the obtaining of high valuable bioactives

The aim is to achieve high extraction yields and high purity bioactives with high stability for new foods, nutraceuticals & cosmetics.

- **A2C TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE RECYCLING OF THE ORGANIC AGRIFOOD WASTES:**

Figure 2. Flowchart of the extraction and revalorisation of food waste from the agrifood industry.

4.1 Process 1: Green hybrid technologies for extraction of bioactive substances from agrifood wastes

4.1.1 Description

This process is in the first phase within the block of the upgrading of fruit and vegetable waste. The process aims to develop the best extraction route of the bioactive substances from the organic wastes. The raw material used for the extraction routes comes from waste from agrifood industries. The residues used are shown below:

Product	Waste (% of generation)
Citrus	Peel, pulp, skins, seeds (50-60%)
Apples	Peel, seeds and cores, exhausted pulp (10-15%)
Grapes	Pomace (peel, seeds, stems and pulp residues) and grape remains (25%)
Artichoke	Leaves and bracts (60-65%)
Cauliflower	Stems, florets not suitable marketing, and leaves (40%)
Broccoli	Stems and florets not suitable for marketing, leaves (25-30%)

Table 2. The fruits and vegetables wastes used for revalorization.

First of all, this raw material is conditioned, choosing a specific treatment according to the type of waste and its state. Among the treatments used are: drying, crushing, grinding, filtering, etc. In this way, concentration and attack surface are increased, which makes the subsequent extraction stages more effective and shortens the time required.

Once the raw material has been conditioned, the bioactive compound extraction stage is carried out. The route chosen will depend on the results obtained in the laboratory scale.

After extraction, on the one hand, the solid part is obtained, which accounts for approximately 20% and contains the fibres, and on the other hand, the liquid part, which accounts for the rest (80%) and contains the phenolic compounds and carotenoids.

To carry out the concentration of the compounds, a purification route is carried out to achieve a suitable composition of each compound.

These routes and expected results can be found below:

Extraction route	Purification tech.	Expected results
Green solvents + ultrasounds assisted extraction	Membrane Filtration	Dietary fibre (Yield \geq 60%, Purity \geq 70%)
	Membrane Filtration + Adsorption	Phenolic compounds & Carotenoids (Yield \geq 60%, Purity \geq 70%)
Green solvents + enzymatic hydrolysis + MW assisted extraction	Membrane Filtration	Dietary fibre (Yield \geq 70%, Purity \geq 80%)
	Membrane Filtration + Adsorption	Phenolic compounds & Carotenoids (Yield \geq 70%, Purity \geq 80%)

Table 3. Extraction and purification technologies.

4.1.2 Energy performance assessment

Consumption is due to the resistors for heating the solutions and the agitators for mixing them.

Due to the fact that the resistors will come into operation depending on the temperature of the solution and the value of the specific heat of the mixture is not available, the energy consumption of the process and its KPIs cannot be obtained until measurements are taken.

4.2 Process 2: New food, nutraceuticals & cosmetic formulations using extracts from agrifood wastes.

4.2.1 Description

The objective of this process is the production of a range of new formulations using the bioactive substances extracted from wastes for their application in cosmetic, nutraceuticals and food.

This process is a continuation of process one. Once the extraction is done, the aim is to separate and stabilise the most interesting compounds for use in nutraceutical, food and cosmetic formulations. In order to do this, filtration is first carried out, separating the solid part from the liquid. The solid part, which accounts for approximately 20% of the total, contains the fibres and the liquid part, which accounts for the remaining part, contains the phenolic compounds and carotenoids.

To stabilise the fibres, the solid part is placed in an oven for dehydration. To obtain the phenolic compounds and carotenoids, a concentration stage is first carried out in which part of the water contained is evaporated, and then, depending on their subsequent use, different stabilisation and conservation processes have been tried out, such as: atomisation, freeze-drying and spray-drying.

The scaling up of this process aims to obtain prototypes for food & nutraceuticals (3000L vegetable desserts, 2000L enriched juices, 20.000 kg-juices&jams, 1000L nutraceuticals), and cosmetic (1 kg antioxidants formulations).

4.2.2 Energy performance assessment

The power, pressures and times indicated in the flow diagram are those expected in the pilot plant, due to the fact that these values are impossible to quantify through laboratory scale tests because almost all the stages are manual and discontinuous. Therefore, as in process 1, the energy consumption of the process and its KPIs cannot be obtained.

(2) Synergistic combination of sorting, physical delamination, enzymatic depolymerisation, decontamination & mechanical recycling for the multilayers recycling and biotransformation processes & extensional flow mixing for the upcycling of the recycled multilayers.

The aim is to obtain a range of high barrier recyclable compounds as alternative to current multilayers in food packaging & agriculture, PHBV bioplastics compounds for biodegradable food packaging & agriculture and carotenoids for cosmetics

Figure 3. Multilayer aseptic bags upcycling.

Multilayer soil disinfection films

Figure 4. Multilayer soil disinfection films.

- **A2C TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE SORTING AND RECYCLING OF THE MULTILAYER PLASTICS COMING FROM AGRICULTURE AND POST-INDUSTRIAL PACKAGING**

4.3 Process 3: Identification and sorting of multilayer materials

4.3.1 Description

The aim of this process is the use of optical sorting to separate the metallised fraction from the multilayer food packaging plastic waste, by a synergistic combination of technologies resulting in the separation of the different multilayers into the fractions:

1. Metallised fraction (PE/met-PET/PE and PE/Al/PA/PE)
2. Non metallised fraction (PE/EVOH, PE, PE/EVOH/PA)

4.3.2 Energy performance assessment

The best optical sorting technology is being analysed. Probably the optical sorting technologies will be installed in continuous processes.

At the moment it is not known which exact optical sorting technologies will be used. The only energy data available is the maximum power consumption without the conveyor belt will be around 2 and 4,5 kW. This value will depend on the final configuration of the technology.

4.4 Process 4: Separation of aluminium (Al) from complex multilayer structures

4.4.1 Description

The objective of this process is the physical separation of the Aluminium from the multilayers based on delamination technology. The result is to obtain separated flows of LDPE/PET, LLDPE/PET, LDPE, PE/PA and Al.

To carry out this process, a large number of equipment is involved.

4.4.2 Energy performance assessment

This process, in contrast to the previous ones, is at a very advanced stage of definition, as its consumption has already been studied for an input of 2,000 kg/h of material to be treated, in which it has been assumed that 40% is PE/met and the remaining 60% is PET/PE-laminate:

INPUT	AMOUNT (kg/h)
Input material from pre-treatment	2.000
Fresh water	4.754
Chemicals	284
OUTPUT	AMOUNT (kg/h)
PE-flakes	739
PET/PE-flakes	1.108
Solid waste (water content 40-70%)	393
Wastewater pre-treatment	3.757
Vapours (in exhaust air)	1.041

Table 4. Material balance of the process.

PROCESS STEP	ELECTRIC POWER DEMAND (kWh)	HEAT DEMAND (kWh)
Delamination	456	875
Washing % Sorting	944	90
Drying	199	800
Water supply	80	0
Wastewater pre-treatment	38	0

Table 5. Process energy demand.

As can be seen from the tables above, two energy sources are needed: electricity and natural gas.

The following KPIs are estimated:

DATA	VALUE	UNIT
Electrical power consumption	0,31 - 0,36	kWh/kg Input (dry)
Natural gas consumption	0,18 - 0,21	kWh/kg Input (dry)
TOTAL	0,49 - 0,57	kWh/kg Input (dry)

Table 6. Process 4 energy consumption.

For the consumption of natural gas (type H) a LHV of 10 kWh/Nm³ and a density of 0.75 kg/Nm³ has been taken.

4.5 Process 5: PET/PE enzymatic depolymerisation

4.5.1 Description

The objective of this project is the depolymerisation of the PE/PET multilayers by a synergic strategy of customisation of enzymes and plastic wastes pre-treatments.

In order for the degradative enzyme to perform its function most effectively, it is first pre-treated by applying heat and humidity while exposing in a UV chamber with a Xenon-arc lamp to increase PE polarity and hydrolyse PET. The UV exposure method will reach 90°C of BST and the Xenon lamp irradiance is going to be 60 W/m² (300nm to 400 nm broadband). Finally, it is processed through an extruder and then through a granulator.

At the same time, in parallel, the enzyme capable of degrading PE/PET is produced in a reactor (in the pilot plant it will be 30 L). Once produced, the mixture will be mixed with the pre-treated PE/PET waste in the appropriate proportion and the enzymatic biodegradation will start (in the pilot plant it will be carried out in a 50 L reactor).

The result is water, which will be treated and recirculated, the enzymes, which will be recovered and the reaction products: alkanes, TPA & EG products, which will serve as input for further processes.

4.5.2 Energy performance assessment

This process is still under study, finishing in month 22, so energy information is limited. The tests carried out are at laboratory scale and in batches in batch, so it is too early to evaluate the energy performance.

Information on energy consumption involves motors (for agitation and centrifugation, movement of conveyor belts, compressors, extruder and granulator) and the use of heating elements for the oven.

4.6 Process 6: Plastics decontamination

4.6.1 Description

The aim of this process is to eliminate 99% of the contaminants that the plastics may contain. This decontamination is carried out in several stages, the first consists of a preliminary washing with water, which will eliminate solvent traces, ground, chemicals and organic contaminants. The water used for washing will be collected and fully recovered through various filtration and treatment processes. Subsequently, a centrifugation process is carried out to remove the water content, followed by a granulation process to achieve the appropriate size. Finally, a vacuum extrusion process is carried out to remove all the Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) and odours.

4.6.2 Energy performance assessment

The energy consumption will mainly come from the pumps to increase the water pressure in the washing process and in the subsequent water treatment processes such as filtrations, which are usually energy-intensive. In addition, there will be consumption of motors to drive the different mechanisms of the centrifuge, the granulator and the vacuum extrusion process, where a compressor is also required.

Energy consumption data are not yet available, so the analysis will be completed in the final deliverable.

4.7 Process 7: Aluminium recycling and chemical modification

4.7.1 Description

The objective of this process is the aluminium purification and treatment for reuse. For this purpose, aluminium from the physical separation will be chemically modified. The result of the chemical modification is that the aluminium achieves optimal compatibility and dispersion in a polyethylene matrix. Two strategies will be investigated:

- i) direct binding of an organic-ligand and further modification with a polyethylene compatible shell
- ii) a two step procedure where the particles are modified with aluminium oxide/silicon oxide in a first step, followed by well-established polymer-shell synthesis protocol.

Finally, the aluminium is dispersed in a matrix of LDPE/EVOH/LDPE and LDPE/PA/LDPE through an extrusion process. These blends will be analysed by serial block-face scanning electron microscopy to obtain real 3D distribution, orientation and concentration of filler materials.

4.7.2 Energy performance assessment

The most efficient route has not yet been selected, so there is not enough data. Once the data from the pilot plant is collected, the analysis will be completed.

- **A2C TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE UPCYCLING OF THE RECYCLED PLASTICS MATERIALS:**

4.8 Process 8: Upcycling of enzymatic degradation products (alkanes, TPA, EG) by cell factories

4.8.1 Description

The objective of this process is the upcycling of enzymatic degradation products (alkanes, TPA, EG) by biotransformation to obtain high added value building blocks for cosmetic:

- Alkanes. Result: ω -hydroxyacids
- Terephthalic acid-TPA. Result: protocatechuic acid.
- Ethylene glycol-EG. Result: glycolic acid.

The best results will be scale up at 10L reactors.

4.8.2 Energy performance assessment

It is foreseen that at least a temperature of 30°C, air inlet (1 vvm) and agitation of 300 to 800 rpm is needed. The expected time per cycle is from 5 to 7 days of fermentation, depending on the amount of substrate fed. The mode of fermentation: fed, and if feasible repeated (fed)-batch. Power and steam will also be required for autoclaving the bioreactors.

This process is still under development, and testing is about to start, so more energy data will be available in the next deliverable.

4.9 Process 9: PHBV and C-50 carotenoids development by *Hfx. mediterranei* haloarchaea cell factory

4.9.1 Description

The objective is the production of PHBV bioplastics and carotenoids by a cell factory. The by-products of the previous cell factories in combination with organic waste from the agri-food industry will be used as nutrients. The result is PHBV for its application in flexible packaging and agricultural films, carotenoids for cosmetics applications.

The work to be carried out to increase the TRL of the process are: upgrading the fermentation of the haloarchaea from lab scale to pilot scale of 100 L and upgrading the extraction process at pilot scale of 1-3 L.

4.9.2 Energy performance assessment

This process has provided some more preliminary information, so that it has been possible to obtain a consumption ratio:

Process/Machine	Power (kW)	Working Time (h)	Consumption (kWh)	
Reactor	1,2	0,5	144	86,4
Tangential filtration	4	1	3	10,5
Centrifugation	6,5	1	2	13,0
Freezer	1	1	24	22,8
Freeze Dryer	4	1	24	96,0
Pump 1	1	1	12	5,3
Pump 2	0,55	0,8	12	5,3
Air compresor	4	1	144	345,6
Thermostatic bath	15	1	144	1.044,0
TOTAL			1.628,9	

Table 7. Energy consumption of the process.

Therefore, this consumption is required to obtain 1 kg of PHBV, the KPI is **1,628.9 kWh/kg**.

4.10 Process 10: High barrier compounds by extensional flow mixing and compatibilisation

4.10.1 Description

The objective of this process is the development of PHBV bioplastics compounds through a synergistic strategy of compatibilisation and extensional flow mixing generation during the extrusion process to develop morphology-controlled blends.

The neat PHBV range obtained will be formulated and compounded for their application in the flexible food packaging and agricultural films development.

4.10.2 Energy performance assessment

There is still not enough information on this process as its development stage has not yet begun (M13). Once data on energy consumption and the machinery involved is obtained, guidelines can be provided to optimise it as much as possible.

5 Conclusions and next steps

The deliverable presents a draft of the energy management plan for the processes and technologies developed in the Agro2Circular, with the aim that once they increase their TRL and reach a semi-industrial scale, they will be as efficient and sustainable as possible.

Due to the fact that the processes are at a very early stage, in this first draft it has only been possible to present the flow diagrams of the processes and some consumption data of those processes that are somewhat more advanced.

Therefore, over the following months, more information will be gathered from the partners carrying out the development of the projects, so that the processes can be defined more concretely. In addition, it will also be possible to provide data on the machinery involved, the energy consumption of each stage of the process (so that the most critical points can be identified), the useful life of each machine involved, the individual and total power demanded, the KPIs and the recommendations on energy efficiency.

